

Educator Insights on Robotics in Schools

This survey aims to gather insights from educators on the use of robots and AI in school education. Your responses will help us to better understand current practices, challenges, and support needs. This survey is part of the EU project ARAISE - Accessible Robotics and AI Supporting Education.

The survey is anonymous and will take approximately 10 minutes to complete.

Thank you for your valuable input!

1. What subject(s) do you teach?

2. Which age groups do you regularly teach?

Check all that apply.

6-10

11-14

15-18

18+

Other: _____

3. How many years of teaching experience do you have?

4. What is your age range?

Mark only one oval.

18-24

25-34

35-44

45-55

55+

5. What is your gender?

Mark only one oval.

female

male

non-binary / third gender

prefer not to say

Robotics in Education

6. I am interested in integrating robots in my lessons.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

7. I am familiar with using robots in my lessons.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

8. Which hands-on technologies or robots have you used or currently use in your lessons?

Check all that apply.

- LEGO Mindstorms (e.g. NXT, EV3, SPIKE)
- mBot
- Bee-Bot
- Ozobot
- BBC Micro:Bit
- Arduino
- Raspberry Pi
- Turtlebot
- Robotont
- Other: _____

The following are **barriers** to using hands-on technology or robots in my classroom.

Rate each statement from Strongly disagree to Strongly agree

9. The cost of hardware is a barrier.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

10. Lack of curriculum alignment is a barrier.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

11. Maintenance/repair issues are a barrier.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

12. Limited classroom space is a barrier.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

13. Language/documentation barriers are a barrier.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

14. Lack of support from school administration is a barrier.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

15. Lack of time is a barrier.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

16. Technological complexity is a barrier.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

17. Lack of student motivation is a barrier.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

18. Other barriers:

The following **competencies** are important for my students.

Rate each statement from Strongly disagree to Strongly agree

19. Computational thinking is important for my students.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

20. Programming basics are important for my students.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

21. Understanding of ethics is important for my students.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

22. Human-robot interaction is important for my students.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

23. Collaborative problem solving is important for my students.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

24. Risks and challenges of AI/Robotics is important for my students.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

25. Other important competencies:

Outlook

26. Following support would make robotics integration easier for me.

Check all that apply.

- Ready-made lesson plans
- Local technical support
- Video tutorials
- Network of teachers
- Funding for kits
- Documentation in native language
- Other: _____

27. I would use a loan-based robot for my school.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

28. I am interested in using more advanced, open-source robots in my lessons.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

29. I would participate in a "train-the-trainer" workshop on advanced, open-source robots for school education.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

30. Any additional comments or ideas you'd like to share about AI/robotics education?

Optional questions

Following questions are country-specific.

31. What is the main focus of your school?

Check all that apply.

- Technical
- Economics
- General Education
- Vocational Education
- Other: _____

32. Where is your school located?

Mark only one oval.

- urban
- rural

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